

CORRECTION

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Correction: Direct visualization of the ouzo zone through aggregation-induced dye emission for the synthesis of highly monodispersed polymeric nanoparticles

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Correction for 'Direct visualization of the ouzo zone through aggregation-induced dye emission for the synthesis of highly monodispersed polymeric nanoparticles' by Eshu Middha *et al.*, *Mater. Chem. Front.*, 2019, 3, 1375–1384.

The authors regret that the ternary phase diagrams shown in Fig. 5 and 7 (in the manuscript) were constructed following analysis 8 hours after mixing solute, solvent and water, instead of immediately after mixing. This results in a shift of the Non-ouzo zone and Binodal line. The Binodal line shifts to a higher solvent fraction with time due to the Ostwald ripening effect. The updated Ouzo diagrams have been added to the ESI file as Fig. S13 and S14 in a new section named '17. Shift in Non-Ouzo zone and Binodal line with time'. The revised ESI file can be accessed *via* the original article.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

